

KGA “XAIR principles” WG – M10 deliverable: Synopsis of core concepts for explainable-AI-ready data and models

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Abstract

Reliable AI technology necessitates the development of robust validation infrastructures and data documentation schemas to ensure that AI systems become trustworthy and transparent. The International Workshop on Designing the Conceptual Landscape for a XAIR Validation Infrastructure (DCLXVI 2024), held on 11th December 2024 in Kaiserslautern, Germany, surveyed the conceptual landscape of explainable-AI-ready (XAIR) models and data. The definition of concepts relevant to data integrity, algorithmic transparency, and user interpretability were explored, resulting in a synopsis of core concepts for “XAIR.”

The DCLXVI 2024 International Workshop explored the potential of metadata standardization as well as conceptual analysis and engineering for AI validation at the state of the art of applied ontology and epistemology. Building explainable-AI-ready (XAIR) digital infrastructures involves ensuring data privacy, addressing ethical concerns, and adhering to regulatory requirements. Standardization is highly relevant to international regulatory efforts, *e.g.*, on digital product passports. At DCLXVI 2024, we investigated the prerequisites at a conceptual level for developing and documenting AI systems that are not only technically robust, but also transparent, interpretable, and trustworthy.

DCLXVI 2024 was organized by three Horizon projects: AI4Work, BatCAT, and DigiPass CSA; it was collocated with a BatCAT consortial meeting, and workshop attendance was included in the BatCAT training programme. The workshop was held on Wednesday, 11th December 2024, in

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Kaiserslautern, Germany, at two sites: The morning session took place at Rhineland-Palatinate Technical University (RPTU); there, DigiPass CSA expert groups and the Knowledge Graph Alliance’s working group on XAIR data and metadata principles were presented. The scientific sessions took place in the afternoon at the Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics (ITWM). This was made possible by Peter Klein, who had joined the organization efforts once it became clear that no room would be available at RPTU – he also showed the workshop participants around ITWM’s fully automated facility for gemstone processing.

A total of 17 manuscripts were submitted for DCLXVI 2024, two of which were desk-rejected. Out of the remaining 15 submissions, 11 were accepted for presentation at the workshop and inclusion in the proceedings [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11] (acceptance ratio 73%, not including the desk-rejected submissions in the statistics). This was done on the basis of at least two reviews for each manuscript (13 of the manuscripts received at least three reviews). This resulted in eight scientific talks at the workshop, three of which were on two papers at once, since they had the same presenting author and the programme committee judged it best to fuse such presentations into one. Four of the presentations were held in person, while the other four were delivered remotely. Out of the 11 accepted papers, four acknowledge funding from both BatCAT and DigiPass CSA [1, 2, 3, 9], and three more acknowledge only BatCAT [4, 5, 7]. Other contributing projects include the Mathematical Research Data Initiative (MaRDI) within the German national research data infrastructure [10] and an initiative for Pakistani-Norwegian collaboration in higher education within the NORPART programme [6].

The papers are grouped into four categories, selected upon paper submission:

1. Discussion of a core concept for explainable-AI-readiness

Papers in this category include a discussion of literature definitions of one specific concept relevant to explainable-AI-readiness. Among the accepted contributions, six are in this category [1, 2, 3, 8, 10, 11]. They identify the following core concepts:

concept	elucidation	ref.
consciousness layer	component of an AI system that applies deductive reasoning to output from a large language model	[2]
DIKW hierarchy	model for value chains in information technology, comprising four levels of cognition and documentation: <i>Data, information, knowledge, and wisdom</i>	[10]
ensemble classifier	AI system that solves a classification problem by combining the output from multiple classifiers	[11]
explanation	artefact giving an account of the following three elements: “What is explained? The explanandum. What gives the explanation? The explanans. What is relating these two? The explanatory relation.”	[8]
neuro-symbolic AI	AI method that combines a neural network with rule-based deductive reasoning	[1, 3]

2. Surveying the landscape of multiple core concepts

Within this theme, contributors were required to provide an analysis of how (or whether) different candidate definitions of two or more concepts relevant to explainable-AI-readiness can be combined with each other. There are two such contributions [5, 9]. The core concepts from these papers include:

concept	elucidation	ref.
predictive performance	degree to which <i>predictions</i> obtained from a model are accurate; various well-established metrics that can be chosen to quantify this.	[5]
scope	what something (<i>e.g.</i> , a simulation) is for, applicable to, or about; dimensions of scope include the <i>subject matter</i> , the <i>object of reference</i> , and the <i>objective</i> .	[9]
simulation artefact	digital artefact that it is advisable to explicitly account for when documenting a simulation; this minimally includes the <i>complete model</i> , the <i>simulation input</i> , and the <i>simulation output</i> .	[9]
transparency	property of a model that allows establishing the trustworthiness and reliability of an AI system using the model; closely related concepts include <i>accountability</i> , <i>explainability</i> , and <i>interpretability</i> .	[5]

3. Applied ontology techniques for visualizing or designing the conceptual landscape

Authors who selected this category were required to apply their techniques to part of the conceptual landscape relevant to explainable-AI-readiness. There are two workshop papers that aim to contribute to conceptual landscape design in this way: Fahad *et al.* [6] develop a landscape of models and explainable AI methods, listing and comparing diverse techniques and neural network types and applying them to endoscopic imagery. Fasouli *et al.* [7], in contrast, address the theme of the workshop more comprehensively. They consider a landscape of “three perspectives, technical, ethical, and user-centric, in the design of a validation system,” where by validation systems, they refer to tools that validate explanations of models and data (as opposed *e.g.* to validating the models and data themselves). They construct a “conceptual framework for XAI validation systems” with four core elements which are roughly aligned with the three dimensions: “Supportive” corresponds to *ethical*, “Inner Core” corresponds to *technical*, and “Outer and Interactive User” corresponds to the *user-centric* perspective.

4. Going beyond FAIR – what is insufficient about the FAIR principles?

Contributions in this category were requested to discuss requirements that are insufficiently addressed by the well-known data management principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR). Only one manuscript submitted for this theme was accepted. Therein, Bashir [4] synthesizes findings from the literature to explore the shortcomings of the FAIR principles and proposes introducing supplementary aspects to be considered when specifying good practices in data management. These are formulated in terms of concepts including *explainable FAIRness*, *privacy-first FAIR*, and *real-time FAIR*.

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